

New combinations in Cucurbitaceae

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Abstract: New combinations are proposed here for 17 species of the family Cucurbitaceae, representing five genera. These nomenclatural changes are necessary to align the species with current taxonomic and phylogenetic concepts accepted for their respective genera. In addition, to ensure accurate application and to stabilize nomenclature, lectotypes are designated for the names *Elaterium glabrum* Cogn., *Microsechium compositum* Donn.Sm., *Microsechium hintonii* Paul G.Wilson and *Sicyosperma gracile* A.Gray.

Keywords: Colombia, Ecuador, *Elaterium*, El Salvador, Endemic, Guatemala, *Gymnopetalum*, Indonesia, Lectotype, Mexico, *Microsechium*, *Mukia*, *Parasicyos*, *Pterosicyos*, *Sechiopsis*, *Sechium*, *Sicyocaulis*, *Sicyos*, *Sicyosperma*, United States of America, *Urceodiscus*

Introduction

Recent molecular phylogenetic studies have significantly altered the generic concepts, delimitation and classification within the family Cucurbitaceae. Based on the current, stable and wider generic circumscriptions in the family Cucurbitaceae (Schaefer, 2007; Schaefer et al., 2009; Schaefer & Renner, 2011; Boer & Thulin, 2012; Sebastian et al., 2012; Telford et al., 2012), new combinations are required for 17 species belonging to five genera (*Cucumis* L., *Cyclanthera* Schrad., *Papuasicyos* Duyfjes, *Sicyos* L. and *Trichosanthes* L.), which are made here. To fix the identity and to avoid misapplication of names, lectotypes are designated here for *Elaterium glabrum* Cogn., *Microsechium compositum* Donn.Sm., *Microsechium hintonii* Paul G.Wilson and *Sicyosperma gracile* A.Gray, because no holotypes were cited in the protologues, and so far, they have not been typified. All lectotypifications follow the

guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2018).

New combinations

Cucumis sumbensis (Pratami) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Mukia sumbensis* Pratami, *Reinwardtia* 21(1): 36, f. 1. 2022.

Holotype: Indonesia, Sumba Island, Taimanga, Kenangar, 15 May 1925, *Iboet* 497 (BO).

Distribution: Endemic to Indonesia (Sumba Island).

Cyclanthera glabra (Cogn.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Elaterium glabrum* Cogn., *Bull. Acad. Roy. Sci. Belgique, sér. 2*, 49: 199. 1880. *Rytidostylis glabra* (Cogn.) Kuntze, *Revis. Gen. Pl.* 1: 258. 1891. *Cyclanthera glabra* (Kuntze) H.Schaef. & S.S.Renner, *Taxon* 60(1): 133. 2011, *nom. inval.* (Article 41.5 of Turland et al., 2018)

Lectotype (designated here): Colombia, in sylvis novae granertae prope Panche, 1250 m, 18 February 1876, *E.F. André* 1666 (NY00172421!, Figure 1); isolectotypes BR0000006604394!, K000424122!, K000424123!.

Distribution: Endemic to Colombia.

Notes: Cogniaux's types are known to be held at BR, LG, NY and U. Four specimens were traced for the name *Elaterium glabrum* Cogn. (BR0000006604394, K000424122, K000424123 and NY00172421). Among these, the better-preserved specimen NY00172421, is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

Papuasicyos scabridulus (Merr. & L.M.Perry) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Melothria scabridula* Merr. & L.M.Perry, *J. Arnold Arbor.* 30: 56. 1949. *Urceodiscus scabridulus* (Merr. & L.M.Perry) W.J.de Wilde & Duyfjes, *Blumea* 51(1): 45. 2006.

Holotype: Indonesia, Indonesian New Guinea, South Papua province, 9 km northeast of Lake Habbema, 2800 m, October 1938, *L.J. Brass* 10621 (A00031919!, Figure 2).

Distribution: Endemic to Indonesia (South Papua province).

Sicyos chinantlensis (Lira & F.Chiang) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sechium chinantlense* Lira & F.Chiang, *Novon* 2(3): 229, f. 1. 1992.

Holotype: Mexico, Oaxaca, San Lucas Ojitlán, del poblado El Zapotal a Mata de Caña, 60 m,

23 January 1989, *J.I. Calzada 14297* (MEXU01226761!).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Oaxaca).

Sicyos compositus (Donn.Sm.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Microsechium compositum* Donn.Sm., Bot. Gaz. 35: 2. 1903. *Ahzolia composita* (Donn.Sm.) Standl. & Steyererm., Publ. Field Mus. Nat. Hist., Bot. Ser. 23: 92. 1944. *Sechium compositum* (Donn.Sm.) C.Jeffrey, Kew Bull. 33(2): 361. 1978.

Lectotype (designated here): Guatemala, Santa Rosa, Malpais, 1100 m, September 1893, *E.T. Heyde & D. Lux 6146* (US00146768!, Figure 3); isolectotypes F0055065F!, GH00031922!, K000424210!, M0189753!, MO016215!, NY00172490!, US00146769!, US00146770!.

Distribution: Guatemala and Mexico (Chiapas, Colima, Guerrero, Jalisco, México and Querétaro).

Notes: The types of D. Smith's new taxa are known to be at US. Three herbarium specimens of *E.T. Heyde & D. Lux 6146* from Malpais, Guatemala were traced at US (US00146768, US00146769 and US00146770). Of these, the best one and better preserved sheet US00146768, is designated here as the lectotype.

Sicyos dieterleae (Lira & R.Torres) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Parasicyos dieterleae* Lira & R.Torres, Acta Bot. Mex. 16: 98. 1991.

Holotype: Mexico, Oaxaca, Municipality Teposcolula, Teposcolula district, Cerro El Peñasco al S de Teposcolula, 2200–2550 m, 9 October 1988, *R. Torres & M.L. Torres 12318* (MEXU).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Chiapas and Oaxaca).

Sicyos dipterus (Kearns) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sechiopsis diptera* Kearns, Syst. Bot. 17(3): 400, f. 3. 1992.

Holotype: Mexico, Chiapas, Municipality of Motozintla, along road to El Porvenir, 8.8 miles north of Huixtla-Motozintla Highway, 2300 m, 22 November 1986, *D.M. Kearns & E. Martinez 542* (MEXU).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Chiapas).

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Elaterium glabrum* Cogn. (NY00172421, © Herbarium of New York Botanical Garden)

Figure 2: Holotype of *Melothria scabridula* Merr. & L.M.Perry (A00031919, © Harvard University Herbaria)

Figure 3: Lectotype of *Microsechium compositum* Donn.Sm. (US00146768, © United States National Herbarium, Smithsonian Institution)

Figure 4: Lectotype of *Sicyosperma gracile* A.Gray (GH00031951, © The Gray Herbarium)

Figure 5: Lectotype of *Microsechium hintonii* Paul G. Wilson (K000424209, © The Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew)

Figure 6: Holotype of *Parasicyos maculatus* Dieterle (F0055066F, © Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago)

Figure 7: Holotype of *Sechium mexicanum* Lira & M.Nee (NY00328814, © Herbarium of New York Botanical Garden)

Figure 8: Holotype of *Sicyocaulis pentagonus* Wiggins (CAS0004574, © California Academy of Sciences)

Figure 9: Holotype of *Sechiopsis tetraptera* Dieterle (MICH1115213, © University of Michigan Herbarium)

Sicyos distinctus (Kearns) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sechiopsis distincta* Kearns, Syst. Bot. 17(3): 405, f. 4. 1992.

Holotype: Mexico, Chiapas, Municipality of Tuxtla Gutiérrez, 2 miles south of Tuxtla Gutiérrez, along road to Villa Flores, c 900 m, 16 October 1965, D.E. Breedlove & P.H. Raven 13363 (MEXU).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Chiapas and Oaxaca).

Sicyos gracile (A.Gray) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sicyosperma gracile* A.Gray, Smithsonian Contr. Knowl. 5(6): 62. 1853.

Lectotype (designated here): Mexico, Sonora, Mountain ravine at Santa Cruz, September 1851, C. Wright 1092 (GH00031951!, Figure 4); isolectotypes GH00254757!, NY00172526!, P06746040!, PH00023824!, TEX00373231!).

Distribution: Mexico (Baja California Sur, Chihuahua and Sonora) and United States of America (Arizona and New Mexico).

Notes: Six syntypes were traced for the name *Sicyosperma gracile* A.Gray (GH00031951, GH00254757, NY00172526, P06746040, PH00023824 and TEX00373231). Of these, the best preserved specimen GH00031951, is designated here as the lectotype.

Sicyos gonzalo-palomae (Lira) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Microsechium gonzalo-palomae* Lira, Anales Inst. Biol. Univ. Nac. Autón. México, Bot. 65(2): 74. 1995.

Holotype: Mexico, Oaxaca, 3 km al norte de La Soledad, en el km 186 de la carretera Oaxaca-Pochutla, 1520 m, 30 October 1990, R. Lira Saade & J.C. Soto 1230 (MEXU01226763!).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Oaxaca).

Sicyos hintonii (Paul G.Wilson) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Microsechium hintonii* Paul G.Wilson, Kew Bull. 13(1): 161. 1958. *Sechium hintonii* (Paul G.Wilson) C.Jeffrey, Kew Bull. 33(2): 360. 1978.

Lectotype (designated here): Mexico, Temascaltepec district, San Lucas, 24 October 1935, G.B. Hinton 8596 (K000424209!, Figure 5); isolectotypes K000424207!, K000424208!, LL00000832!, MICH1115212!, NY00172489!, P02273945!, UC1162542!, US00146771!.

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Colima, Guerrero, Jalisco, México and Michoacán).

Notes: In the protologue of *Microsechium hintonii* Paul G. Wilson, the holotype was not explicitly indicated among the three specimens housed at K (K000424207, K000424208 and K000424209). Therefore, the better-preserved specimen K000424209 is designated here as the lectotype, as it corresponds well with the protologue.

Sicyos laciniatus (Brandeggee) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Pterosicyos laciniatus* Brandeggee, Univ. Calif. Publ. Bot. 6: 72. 1914. *Sechiopsis laciniatus* (Brandeggee) Kearns, Syst. Bot. 17(3): 402. 1992.

Holotype: Mexico, Chiapas, Cerro del Boqueron, September 1913, C.A. Purpus 6915 (UC172957!).

Distribution: Guatemala and Mexico (Chiapas).

Sicyos maculatus (Dieterle) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Parasicyos maculatus* Dieterle, Phytologia 32(4): 289. 1975.

Holotype: Guatemala, Alta Verapaz, hills c 5 km north of San Pedro Carchá, 1200 m, 28 January 1969, L.O. Williams, A. Molina R., T.P. Williams & A. de Molina 40205 (F0055066F!, Figure 6).

Distribution: El Salvador, Guatemala (Alta Verapaz, Baja Verapaz and El Progreso) and Mexico (Chiapas, Oaxaca, Querétaro, San Luis Potosi and Tabasco).

Sicyos mexicanus (Lira & M.Née) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sechium mexicanum* Lira & M.Née, Brittonia 51(2): 204, f. 1. 1999.

Holotype: Mexico, Veracruz, Villa Aldama, 19°40' N, 96°10' W, 2300 m, 24 August 1986, M. Nee 32886 (NY00328814!, Figure 7).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Hidalgo, Puebla, Querétaro, San Luis Potosi and Veracruz).

Sicyos pentagonus (Wiggins) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sicyocaulis pentagonus* Wiggins, Madroño 20: 252. 1970.

Holotype: Ecuador, Galápagos, Santa Cruz Island, c 225 m, 9 February 1964, I.L. Wiggins 18679 (CAS0004574!, Figure 8).

Distribution: Endemic to Ecuador (Galápagos Islands).

Sicyos tetrapterus (Dieterle) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sechiopsis tetraptera* Dieterle, Contr. Univ. Michigan Herb. 14: 69, f. 1. 1980.

Holotype: Mexico, Jalisco, along the main Highway from Guadalajara to Autlán and Barra de Navidad, about 19 km from Melaque, along road to Autlán, c 500 m, 8–9 November 1971, J.V.A. Dieterle 4124 (MICH1115213!, Figure 9).

Distribution: Endemic to Mexico (Colima, Guerrero, Jalisco and Michoacán).

Trichosanthes orientalis (W.J.de Wilde & Duyfjes) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Gymnopetalum orientale* W.J.de Wilde & Duyfjes, Blumea 51(2): 290, f. 5. 2006.

Holotype: Indonesia, West Nusa Tenggara province, Lesser Sunda Islands, Lombok Island, W.J.J.O. de Wilde & B.E.E. Duyfjes 21937 (L).

Distribution: Endemic to Indonesia (Babar Islands, Lesser Sunda Islands, Maluku Islands and Sulawesi).

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